

SURE
SUSTAINABLE
RESILIENT
EU FARMING
SYSTEMS **Farm**

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D6.1 Case-reporting protocol

Work Performed by P2 (KU Leuven) and P3 (ILVO)

Erik Mathijs¹, Jo Bijttebier² and Erwin Wauters²

(Contact: Erik Mathijs)

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¹ Division of Bioeconomics, KU Leuven, Belgium

² Agricultural and Farm Development, Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (ILVO), Belgium

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1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of task 6.1 is to identify integrated sets of conditions that effectively provide an enabling environment for resilient farming systems in Europe. Task 6.1 will integrate findings from workpackages 2, 3, 4 and 5 on resilience enabling conditions and their impact on the attractiveness of the farming sector and its capacity to enhance adaptive behavior and learning. By linking these outcome values to the combinations of conditions, it is possible to identify which combinations of conditions are likely to improve resilience. The results of task 6.1 will feed into task 6.2 where the identified sets of conditions will be translated into guiding principles for a resilience enabling environment. The purpose of this protocol is to make sure that conditions will be characterised comprehensively and systematically across the various case studies.

Figure 1 : WP structure of SURE-Farm

An earlier case-reporting protocol was developed and published as deliverable 6.1. To analyse how conditions in the enabling environment of farming systems interact with resilience and resilience capacities, we drew on the literature on agricultural innovation systems (AIS). A farming system, as defined in this project, is a system hierarchy level above the farm at which properties emerge resulting from formal and informal interactions and interrelations among farms, available

technologies, value chain stakeholders, urban and rural citizens, consumers, policy makers, and the environment (Meuwissen et al., 2018).

The concept of AIS acknowledges that innovation in agriculture—like resilience— is the outcome of an interactive and co-evolutionary process in which a wide range of actors are engaged. Therefore, we assume that this framework can be adapted to study farming systems and the conditions that enable or hinder the resilience of these systems. The protocol was inspired by Lamprinopoulou et al. (2014) and based on the analysis of how the structures (actors, institutions, resources) underpinning a farming system interact with the functions the enabling environment performs to stimulate resilience. This protocol has been further simplified and enriched with resilience concepts from the management literature (Duchek, 2019), resulting in an analytical framework which will be discussed in section 2. Section 3 introduces the methodology to analyse the enabling environment of each SURE-Farm cases study.

2 ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

Farming systems (FS) operate in biophysical, political, social, economic and cultural environments which are often far from stable. Frequently or unfavourably changing conditions can affect FS performance, i.e., the delivery of farming system functions. The dimension and direction of the changes of the environment are often uncertain and there are many unknown unknowns, i.e., events that cannot be imagined currently, let alone that their likelihood is known. Hence, safeguarding the functions of FS requires more than traditional risk management, which often assumes that the possible states of the future environment are known and that probabilities can be attached to each state, i.e., we know which shocks might occur and with which probability. This also means that it is not always clear how FS have to evolve to perform well in the future, since we do not know how that future will look like. Hence, the institutional and socio-economic environment in which farming systems are embedded should at the same time provide some direction to farming systems, but also help farmers keeping their options open and facilitate their flexible and smooth responses. An important policy implication is that to make farming systems resilient, it is not enough to build a safety net—the approach to which most resources are devoted in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Rather, policy should assist farming systems actors to build resilience capacities beyond coping capacity (robustness) – which can amongst others be enhanced through a safety net – but also responsive capacities (adaptability and transformability) through creating an enabling environment that supports adaptations and transformations.

2.1 Defining resilience of farming systems

Resilience capacities refer to the capacity of farms, farmers and farming systems to anticipate (future literacy), cope (robustness) and respond (adaptability and transformability) to shocks and stresses. Actors and institutions in the farming system and in the enabling environment allocate resources in order to produce and support the production of public and private goods (thus fulfilling system functions like food production), but they can also divert resources to invest in resilience capacities. Improving resilience capacities means changing the resilience attributes, i.e., characteristics of the farming system that determine its resilience. Examples of such attributes are sufficient levels of profitability, the level of modularity, the system's openness, the diversity and its flexibility. Resources that are invested and mobilised can be of different forms. Financial resources may be invested in the farm business or set aside to form a buffer to deal with unexpected events. Farmers, farming systems and actors within the enabling environment may also invest in cognitive resources, that is, knowledge and know-how, and network resources, that is, connections and social capital. Physical infrastructure may be built in order to better deal with changes within the environment, examples being storage and sensor technologies. Often, resources are not deliberately reserved for improving resilience attributes, especially those that

support responsive capacities. There can be several reasons for that: farmers may lack resources because they can't build up financial reserves or they have to use most resources for supporting current operational performance or there may be anti-push factors (e.g., attachment to or even vested interest in the status quo) and/or anti-pull factors (e.g., high risk aversion) at play.

Resilient farming systems are those where actors in the farming system and/or in the enabling environment have invested resources into supporting the resilience capacities in such a way that they are able to cope with challenges, i.e., they are robust against external pressure. Robust farming systems are able to continue without having to change, i.e., without having to constantly tap into their responsive capacities in order to trigger a response. Nonetheless, besides coping capacities, responsive capacities have to be present. Indeed, at certain points in time, stresses build up, other types of challenges emerge and/or unanticipated shocks are so severe that farming systems are no longer robust, i.e., they are not able to continue to perform well enough in business-as-usual mode. At that moment, in order to continue to perform, farming systems have to use their responsive capacities in order to respond. Such changes might be modest whereby the main characteristics of the farming system remain intact (adaptations) or they can be more radical changes to the farming system (transformations). The ease with which they can do this reflects their responsive capacities (adaptability and transformability). The goal is to become again robust within the new environment so that they are again able to perform well within the changed environment, without having to constantly change. Further, these responses can also change the characteristics of the farming system in such a way that the resilience attributes and hence the resilience capacities themselves are affected. Anticipating capacities – referring to the capacity to detect trends that could lead to critical changes to the farming system and its environment and to be proactive – influence both the coping capacities and the responsive capacities on the one hand, and the need to use them on the other. As such, farming systems with high anticipating capacities are more resilient. Together, anticipation capacities, coping capacities (robustness) and responsive capacities (adaptability and transformability) determine a farming system's resilience (Duchek, 2019).

Figure 2. A conceptual view on building farming systems' resilience

a Challenges affect farming systems

b Farming systems actors may build and use institutions and invest resources strengthening resilience attributes

b' Farming system actors may invest resources into supporting current performance (functions)

c The enabling environment actors may build and use institutions and invest resources strengthening resilience attributes

c' The enabling environment actors may invest resources into supporting current performance (functions)

d Resilience attributes determine the level of the resilience capacities

e Resilience capacities determine how farming systems can deal with changes through resilience actions

f Resilience actions determine to what extent farming system continues to fulfil functions under the challenges

g Responses (adaptation and transformation) may lead to changes in the farming system, thereby affecting its resilience attributes and capacities.

2.2 Fostering farming system resilience

Fostering farming system resilience means building, mobilising different types of resources. Three questions related to activating these resources for resilience arise: (1) what characteristics of a farming system enable or constrain anticipating, coping and responsive capacities, (2) which actors can – or even should – play which role in building and mobilising resources to develop these capacities, and (3) how should institutions govern investment in and use of resources and capacities?

The first question relates to resilience enabling and constraining attributes, i.e., characteristics of farming systems that affect the anticipating, coping and responsive capacities. Within SURE-Farm, based on the analytical framework developed by Meuwissen et al. (2019), several of such

attributes have been identified. For example, more diverse farming systems tend to be more resilient than highly specialised ones, as more diversity increases the capacity to diversify risks. Farming systems that are more open to new ideas are also more resilient, as they find it easier to adapt to new circumstances. Particularly the second pillar of the CAP stimulates such attributes by providing subsidies for innovation and stimulating networks to exchange ideas, such as the EIP-AGRI. Farming systems that are more profitable can build financial reserves, thereby boosting their coping capacity. Nonetheless, improving resilience enabling attributes and removing resilience constraining attributes is quite complex, especially through single policy instruments only. Often this would require a redesign of the policy mix, as some policy instruments can offset the influence of other. For instance, diversification support policies could improve the diversity and spatial heterogeneity of farms within the farming systems, yet spatial planning policies often lead to a more spatial concentration of farming systems.

The second question relates to the role of actors within and outside the farming system. In farming systems, we can think of several extremes along two dimensions, namely collective versus individual; and private versus public. For instance, resources can be built and mobilised by the government. Agricultural research, especially in areas less attractive to private investors, is often funded by governments as individual farms are too small to set aside meaningful resources for research. Disaster funds are another example. On the other hand, resources can be invested—and capacities built up—by individual farmers, provided they make a profit. Hybrid models exist in which groups of individuals pool resources that may be matched by government funds, as for instance in the case of government-subsidised crop insurance. The question remains then how individuals and groups may have access to capacities and resources. It seems logical that a minimum amount of capacities and resources is needed at the individual level in order to get access to and absorb knowledge developed at the collective level. Whether capacities are built up by mobilising resources in a collective or rather individual way and by public actors, private actors or rather through hybrid ways depends on the type of challenges (e.g., the distinction between normal risk and catastrophic risk), but also on political mechanisms and priorities (e.g., whether society considers it a social or rather individual responsibility to support farmers to managing income volatility), and on historical path dependencies or institutional arrangements across the value chain (e.g., vertically integrated value chains versus spot markets).

The third question relates to the answers on the previous question, as these shape how resources and knowledge are distributed among actors. Information and power asymmetries lead to inequalities in terms of access to resources and capacities. Institutions like the CAP have evolved that determine whether and how capacities and resources can be accessed and activated by those who need it. This also includes gaining insights in institutions (formal and informal rules) that govern behavior of the actors and influence the interactions and relationships among actors.

Institutions encompass a set of common habits, routines and shared concepts used by humans in repetitive situations (soft institutions), organized by rules, norms and strategies (hard institutions). Formal and informal institutions influence how resources (knowledge, money, power) are allocated to activities that help farmers and farming systems to anticipate, cope with and respond to adverse events. For instance, national knowledge and innovation systems may be focused on a limited set of farming system models, paying insufficient attention—and thus resources—to novelty. Private standards that include provisions on the homogeneity of products could be a barrier for system diversity. The first pillar of the CAP plays a huge role here, as it determines who gets subsidies (direct income support and coupled payments) and who not, and also how market management measures may be used.

To conclude, policies and other institutions play an immense role in determining farming system resilience. Both the EU and its Member States allocate resources, but more resources tend to be mobilised to enhance the robustness of farming systems (the safety net approach) than to stimulate adaptation and especially transformation. Fostering farming systems resilience is done through (re)designing institutions and building and mobilising resources in order to enhance resilience enabling attributes of farming systems (and remove resilience constraining attributes). As resources are finite, this could mean prioritising the use of resources to build resilience over the alternative use of these resources to support current performance. The current EU Green Deal, and more specifically its Farm to Fork strategy, while being very systemic in nature, has its core functions in supporting functions (especially the production of public goods) but does not devote specific attention to supporting resilience attributes.

3 METHODOLOGY

The original method would involve that all previous deliverables and reports (and possibly data) had to be consulted again, based on a framework, in order to integrate all previous findings. However, this was considered both methodologically cumbersome and too time-consuming. Hence, a four-step approach has been defined. For each step, you do need to consult data and results from previous tasks, but in a more targeted manner. Do not just copy-paste findings from one single deliverable which seems most relevant, but really integrate findings from different deliverables. For methodologically scrutiny, it is advisable to apply some iteration to this where you start with a prior analysis, and then further improve this through integrating other SURE-Farm results, possibly doing some additional research activities such as targeted interviews or even focus groups. Further, it is also recommended to apply some iteration by doing this task not with just one single person but with a (small) team for further triangulation.

Step 1: Farming system and enabling environment actors and institutions (appr. 3 pages)

List and describe the actors and institutions shaping the farming system and the enabling environment. Try to distinguish between actors in the farming system and in the enabling environment. In SURE-Farm, we have often taken the criterion of mutual influence between farmer and actor as indication that the respective actor belongs to the farming system. Alternatively, but probably leading to the same classification, you could think of actors that are more directly involved in the use of resources for delivering farming system functions as belonging to the FS, and those that influence this delivery rather more indirectly as belonging to the enabling environment. Nonetheless, this definition could be blurry at times, and it is considered that the farming system is a part of the enabling environment, i.e., the enabling environment includes both actors within the farming system and around the farming system, along with the institutions and resources.

It is usually not necessary to list all individuals belonging to an actor group, e.g., ‘farmers’, ‘contractor’, ‘slaughterhouses’ is the kind of ‘actor’ we are looking for. Nonetheless, in cases where a certain actor group only counts one or a few individuals, it could be useful to (1) indicate this and (2) identify them for yourselves so that you can take this into account when doing the ROADMAP focus groups (task 6.2). An example is a sector where, for instance, 3 companies control, through vertical integration, the majority of production. Here, the practices and roles of these very few individuals can be very influential. Organise the actors and corresponding institutions in five actor domains (enterprise, government, intermediary, Agricultural and Knowledge Innovation Systems (AKIS) and society) and summarise this information in a table as in Table 1. The term Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) refers to the whole

knowledge exchange system at the regional or country level. Include most important actors of the AKIS relevant to your farming system.

Whether an actor is classified as “enterprise domain”, intermediary or AKIS, is not so important. The categories are there to give structure and make sure certain groups of actors are not forgotten.

List all the institutions and structure them according to the actor who has been most instrumental in creating these institutions (realizing that sometimes this may not be clear, or several actors may have been involved). List both formal and informal institutions (or hard and soft institutions). Formal are those that are really regulations (e.g., fiscal policy, private standards, CAP, nitrate directive, ...); informal are institutions that equally guide actors’ practices and interactions between them but are unwritten and not formally institutionalized in regulation (e.g., local customs with regards to cooperation, level of representation in policy design, common visions on the ideal farm, ...). List both public (by all government levels and domains) and private (by business actors such as processors, retail, farmers, ...) institutions.

There have been several SURE-Farm tasks and deliverables where you could look for this information, and restructure it a bit, amongst others (not an exhaustive list)

- D3.1 Report on current farm demographics and trends for selected regions
- Task 5.2 Fopia
- Task 2.4. Co-creation of improved risk management strategies (risk management workshops)
- Task 2.2. Farmers’ adaptive behavior (adaptive learning interviews).
- WP 4. Analysis regarding institutions (policy, mainly CAP)

Table 1: Actors in the Belgian dairy farming system and its enabling environment (for illustration only, not an exhaustive list for the Belgian case-study).

Actors	Formal institutions	Informal institutions
Enterprise domain: PO BesteMelk, PO Dairycam, PO Milcobel Input suppliers (feed, technology, fertilizer, pharmaceuticals), dairies, retailers, banks, insurance companies	PO	Attitude towards cooperatives Attitude towards retail
Government domain: European Union FPS Health, food chain safety and environment Department of Agriculture & Fisheries Department of Environment, VMM, VLM Provinces, Municipalities	CAP, Nitrates Directive Food Law CAP Nitrates Directive, CAP	Accountability Farmer participation Societal participation
Intermediary domain: Liba, DLV, SBB, MTC IKM, BO MilkBE, BCZ Boerenbond, ABS, Bioforum	Futures IKM, interbranch	Ideal form of chain collaboration Ideal farmer type
AKIS domain: ILVO, UGent, KU Leuven, Thomas More, Hooibeekhoeve	Agrolink	Technical vision on farming
Societal domain: BBL, Greenpeace, WWF		Societal vision on farming

Step 2: Identify challenges and adverse events in the last 10 years (appr. 2 pages)

Describe the main challenges/adverse events (between 5 and 10) of the farming system. Try to list the main challenges/adverse events that have challenged your farming system in the past decade including those that currently challenge the farming system (for instance you can but are not obliged to include COVID-19 here if that is relevant).

Try to describe what was really the challenge, rather than describing the symptom or consequence. For instance **‘low profitability’ may be mentioned by farmers as a challenge, and it probably is something challenging to deal with, but this is rather expressed as a consequence of challenges in terms of poor delivery of system functions (in this case ‘income generation’).**

For each challenge, try to identify whether it was/is (based on Maxwell, 1986):

- **A sudden shock.** Something that is usually not foreseen by farmers, researchers or other stakeholders. Here you can be quite flexible in the time dimension of 'sudden' and the unexpectedness dimension of 'sudden'. For instance, for dairy farming systems, the quota abolishment can be categorised as a shock, even though it was announced well ahead of the actual end of the quota system. For instance, COVID-19 be categorised as a shock, even though some claim that a pandemic this size could have been foreseen.
- **A trend** (or stress in SURE-Farm language): gradual changes that are more easy to predict than shocks but not less important. Examples are increasing societal pressure to produce more sustainably, declining real farm gate prices, increasing pressure on land from non-agricultural stakeholders, Here, it could be interesting not to look only at stress (negatively perceived trends) but also at more neutral trends, e.g., the increasing digitisation of farming, i.e. to broaden this analysis from challenges to opportunities and trends.
- **Noise (normal variation):** the kind of variation that occurs regularly, that is usually not such a surprise as shocks, and usually less challenging than stress (trends). Examples are weather variability, moderate price volatility, rainfall variability. Of course, within this normal variation, sudden shocks might appear which are more severe (e.g., price drops to levels outside normal variation) and they can become stress (e.g. rainfall variability which become gradually more variable)
- **Cycles.** This is a type of change which does not often occur (anymore) in socio-ecological systems such as farming systems, but some challenges could be in this category. Commodity price cycles are an example, but even those seem to be more a phenomenon of the past. Hence, his category is mentioned here for the sake of completeness, but don't hesitate to use it when relevant.

At this step 2, DO NOT limit your thinking to challenges that really affected the delivery of system functions (since we also want to identify challenges that did not affect the delivery of function in order to understand why this did not happen) and DO NOT limit your thinking to challenges that were always followed by a clear response (since we also want to identify challenges that did not require a clear response and understand why not).

Step 3: Response analysis (appr. 5-10 pages)

For all identified challenges, do the following substeps

3.1 Analyse the **(possible) impact** of these challenges of the delivery of system functions.

- Describe what the impact COULD HAVE BEEN (regardless of whether that impact occurred or not) on the delivery of system functions. Which function was in danger – or would have been changed possibly also in a positive sense when looking at opportunities rather than trends – and how?
- Describe whether that impact really did occur or not. Try to reason **in general terms** why the possible impact eventually happened or not, a more structured analysis is done in the next sub-steps.
- Example: “For the Belgian dairy farming system, a current ‘trend’ is drastically increasing total milk production, which jeopardizes the ‘maintaining natural resources in good conditions’ function. This impact did occur with respect to nitrate (the share of nitrate pollution coming from bovines increased), but did not happen with respect to climate change. Production increased by more than 30%, but greenhouse gas emissions decreased by 6%. This was the result of increases in cow productivity (through technological innovations regarding feed, milking systems, health, and genetics) which meant greenhouse gas emission per liter offset the increased in total liters produced. However, this was more a convenient side-effect of innovation with the mere intent to boost productivity and profitability rather than a deliberate response to safeguard the ‘maintaining natural resources in good conditions’ function.

3.2. Describe if and how this challenge has been **anticipated**

- Describe if and how this event has been anticipated.
- Describe if this anticipation has helped to alleviate the potential impact on the delivery of system functions or not (see above, you previously has to describe what the POTENTIAL impact on the delivery of system function could have been, and whether this impact has occurred or not)
- Describe in both cases (whether anticipation has helped to alleviate the impact or not) what has helped to anticipate this challenge (or what was lacking which could have helped to alleviate this challenge in the case the challenge had an impact). While describing what has helped, think of
 - o Actors and what they do/did
 - o Institutions that are being used or implemented by the actors
 - o Resources that actors used/invested/built (social capital, financial capital, economic capital, human capital, infrastructural capital, cultural capital, symbolic capital, ...)

3.3 Describe if and how the farming system has been able to **cope** with this challenge

- If the potential impact did not occur, has this been because the farming system was able to cope with it (deal with it without changing)?
- If yes, describe what helped to cope with it. Again, think of

- Actors and what they do/did
- Institutions
- Resources that are/were invested/used/built
- If the potential impact did occur, what has made the farming system vulnerable? Which characteristics were lacking?

3.4. Describe if and how the farming system has been able to **respond** to this challenge

- If the potential impact did not occur, has this been because the farming system was able to respond (deal with the impact through changes to the farming system)
- What helped in making this change possible? Here as well, think of
 - Actors
 - Institutions
 - Resources
- What kind of responses have been implemented? How did this change the farming system?
- If the potential impact did occur, the farming system was likely not able to respond (change) adequately. Why not? What was lacking?

Step 4: Pattern analysis (appr. 5 pages)

Try to find overall patterns in the previous analyses. The use of the system archetypes (Kim, 2000, see Annex 1) is useful here. It is a typology of systemic issues and possible solutions. Use the archetypes to

- Classify each event you analysed above into one of the archetypes if possible. Use the archetypes thinking to improve the analysis you produced in step 3 (regarding why challenges had an impact or not and the role therein of actors, institutions and resources).
 - When the farming system has demonstrated good resilience because the potential impact did not occur, or only limitedly, because the farming system was able to anticipate and/or cope and/or respond), use the archetypes to improve your analysis of why.
 - When the farming system did not demonstrate good resilience, again use the archetypes, but now in order to demonstrate the systemic failures and possible solutions that were lacking.

Try to find patterns – if they exist – across types of challenges (shock, stress (trends), noise, cycles). For instance, does the farming system behave differently in terms of resilience against shock or stresses (trends), noise and cycles?

Try to find patterns across system functions that are in danger. Do you see the same pattern depending on which function is in danger or not? Can you identify reasons for differences if they exist?

Try to summarise your findings in terms of roles and practices of actors; institutions that guide their actions and interactions between the actors; and resources they invest in order to, deliberately or not, build farming system resilience. Try to link your summary, possibly in a table, with resilience attributes that are strengthened or weakened in this way.

4 TIMING

Start CS work	13 July 2020
Presentation BE CS and Q&A	8-10 September 2020 (Project Meeting)
Case study reports	31 October 2020
Draft deliverable	31 December 2020
Final deliverable (D6.2)	31 January 2021
Policy brief (D6.3)	31 January 2021

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6 Annex 1. Diagnosing systemic issues through systems archetypes thinking

Systems-Archetypes-I
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